

The definition of tokens in relation to words and annotation tasks

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Abstract

Tokens are the basic units of annotations. When working with corpora of non-standardized texts, tokenization is often problematic, as the usage of whitespace can vary. We show examples of how decisions in the tokenization process can influence an annotation and argue that the principles underlying the tokenization should be grounded in theoretical concepts selected on the basis of the annotation task. We present a corpus of Early New High German texts in which the annotation layers reference two different concepts of words: syntactic words and graphematic words. Consequently, we use two kinds of tokens: graphic tokens and syntactic tokens.

1 Introduction

This paper concerns tokens, which are the basic units of annotations. The tokenization process is therefore decisive for all further annotation, including the assignment of part-of-speech (PoS) tags and syntactic analysis. For languages with alphabetic scripts, tokens are roughly defined by the appearance of whitespace (cf. Schmid [10]). In the modern, standardized, written variants of English and German, tokens defined in this way generally coincide with syntactic words. However, even in texts that are close to standard, there are cases in which the boundaries of tokens as defined by whitespaces and those of syntactic words do not align (cf. Grefenstette / Tapanainen [6]). This leads to divergent tokenizations in different corpus projects, which impacts the resulting annotations. Using the example of contractions, we show the consequences of tokenization choices for the creation of treebanks and the assignment of PoS tags. From this, we conclude that tokenizations should be determined on the basis of the annotation task at hand. We present a corpus of Early New High German (ENHG) protocols of witch interrogations as a case study for the implementation of multiple tokenizations that are each motivated by specific annotation tasks.¹

¹This corpus is created as part of the project “Development of Sentence-internal Capitalization in German” (SIGS), funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG). Two of the three authors

2 Different tokenizations – different annotations

A typical case in which deviations between whitespaces and syntactic words emerge is the use of non-standard contractions in direct speech in newspaper texts. The segmentation rules applied in TüBa-D/Z, a treebank of Modern German newspapers (Telljohann et al. [11]), distinguish between cliticized verb-pronoun combinations marked by an apostrophe, such as *gibt's* (< *gibt* + *es* ‘it exists’), and non-standard graphic contractions without apostrophes, such as *glaubense* (< *glauben* + *sie* ‘you believe’). Only in the first case is the contraction split into two tokens. Because the token is the basic unit of the syntactic annotation in the treebank, the syntax tree shows no trace of the merged subject pronoun in *glauben=se*. Consequently, two similar constructions are treated differently when graphic (rather than syntactic) rules are used for the tokenization. This shows that graphic tokenization rules can lead to inconsistencies in the subsequent syntactic analysis.

Because TüBa-D/Z, which consists of 1.5 million tokens, contains only 56 instances in which a token includes more than one syntactic word, the problem is negligible.² In contrast, in corpora of non-standardized texts (such as internet-based communication and historical documents), such cases are much more common. Therefore, the tokenization must be more carefully conceptualized and applied. A comparison of different adaptations of the German PoS tagset STTS (Schiller et al. [9]) to non-standardized texts shows that the definition of tokens can have far-reaching consequences for subsequent annotation layers.

For internet-based communication, Bartz et al. [1] propose to treat contracted forms such as *machste* (< *machst* + *du* ‘you make’), as one token. To this end, a new tag class for contractions is introduced. The tags in this class consist of the prefix KTR and parts identifying the constituents of the contraction (for the above contractions of verb and pronoun, KTRVPPER).

Contracted forms are also frequent in historical texts. However, the adaptation of STTS to historical texts, HiTS (Dipper et al. [3]), does not make use of specific tags for contracted forms because the written texts are first “normalized” – that is, they are segmented into units that approximate the tokens of modern, standardized, written German. By means of this procedure, contracted forms such as *machste* are separated. The HiTS tagset itself is only applied to the units of the normalized tokenization.

These examples make it clear that different tokenizations yield different annotations, thus, emphasizing the importance of the careful definition of tokens, especially when dealing with non-standardized texts. We argue that this definition should not be based on graphic conventions; instead, tokenizations should be motivated by linguistic concepts of the unit word, which in turn must be defined with respect to a specific linguistic level (cf. Zwicky [13], Fuhrhop [5]). Furthermore,

of this paper, Fabian Barteld and Renata Szczepaniak, are collaborators in this joint project with the University of Münster (Klaus-Michael Köpcke and Marc Schutzeichel).

²Here we are referring to TüBa-D/Z Release 9 (11.12.2013) in which these cases are marked at the lemma level.

different annotations or applications may call for different tokenizations (cf. Chiarcos et al. [2]). As a consequence, when multi-layer annotations are being created, multiple tokenizations may be necessary.

In the following section, we will present the tokenization approach used in the SIGS project, which is in the process of creating a corpus of Early New High German texts. SIGS defines two levels of tokenization: one based on a graphematic concept of words, and the other on a syntactic concept.

3 Case study: Graphic and syntactic tokens in a corpus of ENHG texts

In the SIGS project, a corpus of protocols of witch interrogations, written between 1570 and 1670, (Macha et al. [7]) is being annotated to analyze the spread of word-initial capitalization in Early New High German (ENHG). Word-initial capitalization in German started as a pragmatic marker (emphasizing certain words); it later developed into a syntactic marker (marking the head of a nominal phrase). In this project, we analyze how multiple factors (e.g., the syntactic function, the semantic role and the animacy of a noun’s referent) interacted in this development. To this end, the corpus is annotated in multiple layers, one of which is the syntactic constituency. As noted above, using graphic rules to segment a text into tokens can result in similar structures being annotated differently. This is further illustrated by example (1),³ which shows two types of mismatches between whitespaces and syntactic words: preposition-article contractions and the spelling of compounds as separate words.

- (1) a. auff=m Teufel-β dantz
 at=[the]DAT devil-LE dance[DAT]
 at the devil’s dance
 (Alme 1630)
- b. in=s teufel-β Nahme-n
 in=[the]GEN devil-GEN name-DAT
 in the name of the devil
 (Alme 1630)⁴

In both parts of example (1), the units that are separated by whitespaces would be analyzed with the same parts of speech according to STTS – namely, APPRART, NN, and NN. However, these two graphically identical structures are syntactically different. (1a) includes the separated compound *Teufelβ dantz* (‘devil’s dance’). Hence, syntactically speaking, the phrase contains only one noun, whereas (1b) contains two nouns. Furthermore, the preposition-article contraction *auffm* in (1a)

³The glosses in the examples follow the Leipzig Glossing rules (<http://www.eva.mpg.de/lingua/resources/glossing-rules.php>). LE here means “linking element”.

⁴ Place and Year of the protocoll reference the text in the edition of Macha et al. [7].

includes an article that agrees in case (dative) with the head noun *Teufels dantz*. In contrast to Modern German, ENHG also allows contractions when the article is part of an embedded genitive phrase. In example (1b) the article contained in the contraction *ins* agrees in case (genitive) with *teufelß*, which modifies *Nahmen*.

These syntactic differences can easily be seen in Fig. 1 in which the graphic units *auffm* and *ins* are treated as separate tokens and the two graphic units *Teufelß* and *dantz* are merged.

Figure 1: Syntactic annotation based on syntactic tokens

This example also indicates the relevance of the syntactic structure for capitalization. In both phrases, the only capitalized graphic unit is the beginning of the head of the noun phrase immediately dominated by the PP. However, if we only tokenized in this way (which is similar to the normalization process in Dipper et al. [3]), we would lose the possibility of referring to simple alphabetic strings that are delimited by whitespaces (i.e., to the unit that can be capitalized). Examples (2) and (3) show two cases in which compounds (indicated by brackets) are graphically separated and the second part is capitalized.

- (2) drey stuckh [rindt Viech]
 three pieces cattle cattle
 three pieces of cattle
 (Baden-Baden 1628)
- (3) der zu geordneten [Gerichts Schöpfung]
 the to allocated court jury
 the allocated jury
 (Georgenthal 1597)

In the SIGS project, we use two tokenizations, which will be described in the following two sections. The different layers of the annotation can then be based on either of the two tokenizations. Using the ANNIS interface, the two tokenizations can be queried and combined (cf. Zeldes [12]).

3.1 Graphematic words and graphic tokens

When investigating capitalization, the fundamental units need to be based on the graphic form. The relevant word concept related to the graphic form is defined as the “graphematic word”. Fuhrhop [5] proposes a formal definition of the graphematic word in German: Basically, a graphematic word stands between two spaces and does not itself contain spaces. This definition is similar to many definitions of tokens. However, her concept also entails differences in relation to common approaches of tokenization. For example, Fuhrhop suggests that sentence final punctuation marks should be viewed as belonging to a graphematic word. She therefore treats a form like *<denken.>* (‘to think’) as a distributional variant of the form *<denken>*, similar to intonational differences that can be found in phonological words depending on their context.

The graphematic word, however, cannot be directly used as the basic unit for the study of the development of capital letters. Here, even units smaller than graphematic words are relevant. In the SIGS corpus, a number of instances similar to example (4) can be found.

- (4) *ge-* <linebreak> *Antwortt*
PTCP *answer*
answered
(Erkelenz 1598)

In this example, we see a graphematic word divided after the participle prefix *ge* at the end of a line. The hyphen indicates that the two parts form one graphematic word (cf. Fuhrhop [5]); the problem is that the second part of the graphematic word (*Antwortt*) starts with an uppercase letter. In order to investigate such capitalizations, the second part of the graphematic word must be annotated on its own. Hence, initial capitalization can be related to units smaller than graphematic words. The relevant units should be defined as non-whitespace characters surrounded by whitespace characters (which include the linebreak). The SIGS project uses this definition for the graphic tokens. For the annotation of such graphic tokens with PoS tags, we need tags for contractions such as those defined by Bartz et al. [1], as well as tags for parts smaller than the units that are normally annotated in PoS tagging – e.g., for the prefix *ge-* in example (4).

3.2 Syntactic words and syntactic tokens

Syntactic words can be defined as the basic units of a sentence (cf. Fuhrhop [5]) and therefore represent a good basis for the tokens in syntactic annotations, as illustrated in example (1). In the SIGS corpus, there are nine different types of mismatches between graphic tokens and syntactic words: (i) words split at the end of a line, (ii) verb particles graphically separated from the verb, (iii) compounds written as separate words, (iv) the infinitive particle *zu* (‘to’) merged with

the verb, (v) pronominal adverbs such as *davon* written as separate words, (vi) clitics and contractions, (vii) univerbations such as *allweg* (‘always’ < ‘all’ + ‘ways’) written as separate words, (viii) words that have been deleted (e.g., by means of strikethroughs), and (ix) catchwords.⁵

Most of these types are also mentioned in Dipper et al. [3]. The two interesting cases that are not mentioned there are deleted words and catchwords. In both cases, graphic tokens exist that should not appear at the level of the syntactic annotation, as they would be superfluous. However, at the level of the graphic token, it is important to retain them, as they can be relevant with regard to capitalization (see Fig. 2, in which the two instantiations of *vnnd* differ in terms of capitalization).

Text	Inn einem stotzen gepracht, vnnd <pagebreak> Vnnd zu getragenn,									
Graph. Token	Inn	einem	stotzen	gepracht	,	vnnd	Vnnd	zu	getragenn	,
Synt. Token	Inn	einem	stotzen	gepracht	,	vnnd			zugetragenn	,
Translation	In	a	drinking vessel	brought	,		and		brought	,

Figure 2: Tokenizations of an ENHG example containing a catchword (Georgenthal 1597)

The SIGS corpus is still under construction. At the time of writing (November 2014), a pre-final tokenization of 18 protocols exists, which thus far consists of 26,709 annotated graphic tokens and 26,158 syntactic tokens. In 24,893 cases, the graphic and syntactic tokens are equivalent, but 1,816 (6.8%) graphic tokens and 1,265 (4.8%) syntactic tokens deviate from each other.

4 Conclusion and outlook

In this paper, we have illustrated how different tokenizations can lead to different annotations. Consequently, the choices behind the tokenization should be based on theoretical assumptions relevant to the specific annotation task and should be made explicit in the annotation guidelines. This is especially important when creating a corpus of non-standardized texts, as there can be substantial variation in the usage of whitespace.

Tokens are often intended to resemble words. However, because the boundaries of words differ on different linguistic levels, the specific concept of “word” underlying the tokenization process must be selected on the basis of the annotation or application. We have given two examples of the definition of tokens based on graphematic and syntactic words. Furthermore, we have shown the need for multiple tokenizations in a project examining the multiple factors behind the development of sentence-internal capitalization in German, as the different annotation layers reference different concepts of words. Depending on the corpus and the aims of the annotation, other types of tokens might be useful, such as tokens based on phonological words in corpora of spoken language (cf. Eckart et al. [4], Rehbein / Schalowski [8]).

⁵Catchwords are repetitions of the first word on a page at the bottom of the previous page, which were used as an aid for binding the pages in the right order.

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